

NDAC SIMULATIONS OF DOUBLE AND MULTIPLE STARS:
DETECTABILITY AND ASTROMETRIC ACCURACY[†]

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ABSTRACT - In order to test the feasibility of different reduction methods, simulated observations for a large number of doubles and multiples have been analyzed. It is shown that useful results may be obtained for "known" systems, but mainly that HIPPARCOS will also be able to discover unknown doubles and triples. Realistic discovery-limits in sep/ Δm are given for the first time.

1. INTRODUCTION

The outstanding "problem objects" in the HIPPARCOS reductions are the double and multiple stars. Using several different criteria, these "trouble stars" have to be flagged and excluded from the main reductions. Special post-mission procedures are then used to extract as much information as possible about them. An overview of the methods to be used by NDAC is given by Lindegren (ref. 1).

Before writing the software for these reductions, we are making rather extensive simulations and test programs. The present paper discusses some main results from these tests, further details may be found in refs. 2-8.

2. OBSERVATION SIMULATION

For a given "trouble object", a mission and instrument model gives the complete set of IDT observations. The scanning is "schematic" (gaussian deviations from the nominal, no eclipse interruptions), but for the present purpose it should suffice. The instrument model uses the large-scale grid distortion and a detailed OTF-model including colour-dependent modulation amplitudes and phase errors. For each frame where the object is observed, the individual IDT-counts are calculated, but they are preprocessed directly to five Fourier coefficients (and their mean errors). These five parameters per frame are the basic data used by the different analysis programs. (For wide

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doubles, the IFOV pointing may be different for the two components. In this case, ten parameters per frame are obtained, five for each pointing.) See also ref. 9.

3. REDUCTION PRINCIPLES

The real analysis is made after the main reductions are completed, thus a "true" reference phase and the exact scan-geometry are available. The only unknowns are the parameters describing the multiple object, and a standard non-linear iterative least squares adjustment of these parameters are made with the IDT Fourier coefficients as "observations".

The differential coefficients $\partial(\text{Fourier coeff.})/\partial(\text{model parameter})$ may be calculated analytically, as also a simple weighting that takes the IFOV pointing and -profile into account. Both theoretically and in practice, it is advantageous to use only the first and second harmonic amplitudes and phases, not the total intensity. In the real reductions, these Fourier coefficients will be averaged over each FOV-passage, but in most of the test runs, there are four coefficients for each frame, 4704 in all for a "typical" position at latitude 32° .

The main difficulty is to find start values for the model parameters that ensure a convergent LS-process. Either one has to know (within some $0''.2$) the positions of all the components, or one may iterate also the start values. When the start values are good enough, the least squares process converges in about five iterations, giving final estimates for the astrometric parameters. In the simulation tests, the estimated parameters may be compared with the true (input) ones to give a measure of the astrometric accuracy. See further below.

4. KNOWN DOUBLES AND MULTIPLES

For known double or n-tuple stars (with linear orbital motion over 2.5 years), an obvious $6n$ -parameter model (five astrometric parameters and a magnitude for each component) may be used. In my previous notes (refs. 2, 3, 5, 7), I have assumed that the a priori positions for all components are known to within some $0''.2$, but this is generally true only for the relative coordinates. The absolute position of the primary has generally its Input Catalogue uncertainty, and a "grid-search" (analogous to that described below for an unknown secondary) has to be used to find a better start value. This has now (ref. 8) been found to work well for a number of binaries and multiples. Twelve grid-points suffice if the a priori position is within about 1.5 arcsec from the true one, otherwise this number may be increased. The relative positions need to be known to within $0''.3$ for binaries, shrinking to about $0''.15$ for quintuples (depending largely on the magnitude differences and their errors).

The astrometric accuracy of the resulting solution may be conveniently specified (for one component or for the photocentre) by

$$\text{rms}(\text{astr}) = \left[\frac{1}{5} \{ (x_s - x_t)^2 + (y_s - y_t)^2 + (\pi_s - \pi_t)^2 + (\dot{x}_s - \dot{x}_t)^2 + (\dot{y}_s - \dot{y}_t)^2 \} \right]^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

where subscripts s and t stand for solution and true, and where a yearly proper motion is given equal weight as a position. Such astrometric rms-errors have been determined for a variety of systems, and for doubles the variation with separation is typically as shown in Fig. 1 for equal-magnitude systems. For "trapezium type"-multiples, (separations 2-7" between nearest neighbours), the astrometric errors are only somewhat larger than for similar doubles. The "total weight" Σrms^{-2} for an n-tuple diminishes with n, but only to about 2/3 at n=5 vs n=2.

Fig. 1. Mean astrometric errors for the components in equal-magnitude systems of different brightness. Typical error-bars indicated at right.

The important comparison of these actual astrometric errors with those given by the inverse NE matrix shows no gross inconsistencies. The real errors are larger than the formal ones by only about 20%.

5. DOUBLE STAR DETECTION

For a large number of previously unknown binaries, the goodness-of-fit measures accumulated during the regular processing will indicate probable multiplicity. In order to determine the parameters for these suspected binaries, it is necessary to make an extra "grid iteration" of the standard LS process. (In this case, we may assume that the

normal processing has given a good enough start position for the primary. The iteration is for a suspected secondary component.) If we do not get convergence with one assumed separation/PA, another is tried from a grid of twelve (four points at sep=0".35, eight at sep=0".85). The intensities are less critical, thus a start value 1.0 for the magnitude difference between the components always works. The definition of convergence may be delicate. One has to select a maximum χ^2 error for the fit to the observations, below which an apparently convergent solution is accepted. Solutions with slightly poorer fit are saved until all grid-points have been tested, and only then the minimum is selected.

To test this "discovery mode", a number of quasi-realistic binaries have been generated. For given magnitudes, separation and period, a binary with consistent masses, colours and distance is created, and its exact orbital positions are used in the simulation program. For comparison with the standard analysis results, a linear approximation to the individual positions and proper motions is also given. (In practice, very few systems will give problems due to nonlinear orbital motion, cf. ref. 6.) With guidance from the results in ref. 10, a uniform distribution over $\lg$ sep and a corresponding gaussian $\lg$ P distribution (mean $\lg$ P(years)=3.3+1.5* $\lg$ sep(")) was assumed for three different values of the primary H-magnitude, and several hundred test binaries were generated.

The analysis is made in two steps. First, a single-star solution is made, and then the double-star grid search. The output from either is a goodness-of-fit χ^2 measure S (ideally with nob's d.o.f.), and secondly the actual astrometric errors as compared with the true values. With regard to S, one may divide the solutions into three groups:

- 1(s) : $S(\text{sing}) < S_1, S(\text{sing})-S(\text{bin}) < s_1$
- 2(b) : $S(\text{sing}) - S(\text{bin}) > s_1$
- 3(p) : $S(\text{sing}) > S_1, S(\text{sing})-S(\text{bin}) < s_1$

The actual values for S_1 and s_1 may be adjusted; for the standard case nob's=4704 I have used mostly $S_1=5000$, $s_1=400$. Neglecting the small p ("problem") category, we may say that useful binary parameters are obtained for the b ("binary") category, while a single-star solution is sufficient for the s ("single") systems. In order to include all b-stars, the flagging of suspected binaries in the preprocessing stage of the real reductions will have to be rather generous. The above analysis may well indicate that some one third of the systems are in the s-category.

The b/s-distinction is so far based only on the χ^2 fit to the observations. For the best-studied case (primary mag $H_1=8.5$, 32° latitude), Fig. 2 gives a plot of the b- and s-stars in the ($\lg$ sep/ Δm)-plane. A good division is given by the straight lines indicated. For separations above some 0".32, we have a $dH_{\max}=3.4$ such

that systems with larger magnitude difference are observed as singles. For smaller separations, the border-line is taken simply as

$$dH = 5.5 \lg \text{ sep} + 6.12 \quad (2)$$

down to a minimum separation about $0''.11$ - $0''.12$. Systems with smaller separations will not be discovered as double, even at $dH=0$.

Fig 2. (8.5 primary, lat 32 deg)

Fig 3. (6.0 primary, lat 32 deg)

Fig 4. (11.0 primary, lat 32 deg)

Fig 5. (8.5 primary, lat 12 deg)

Figs. 2-5. Distribution of b- and s-systems in the $\lg \text{ sep}/\Delta m$ -plane. Slope of inclined border-line is 5.5 mag per dex in $\lg \text{ sep}$.

It might be assumed that $dH_{\text{max}} = 3.4$ is due to a magnitude cut-off for the secondary. Fig. 3 gives dH_{max} the b/s-plot for systems with $H_1 = 6.0$, but the increase is only to about $dH_{\text{max}} = 4.2$, $\text{sep}_{\text{min}} = 0''.10$. Thus, even for bright stars, a secondary more than dH_{max} about 4 magnitudes fainter than its primary will go unnoticed. There is of course a real magnitude limit as seen for $H_1 = 11.0$ in Fig. 4. Here, as expected, no secondary below $H = 13.5$ is detected, and the minimum separation is about $0''.17$.

Figs. 2-4 are all for a position on the sky at ecliptic latitude 32° . The analogue of Fig. 2 at latitude 12° is shown as Fig. 5. The "standard" border of Fig. 2 is indicated, and it appears thus that the effect of different scan-geometries is relatively minor.

The above dH - and separation-limits are significantly worse than the estimates by Lindegren in ref. 11. The reason for this is unclear, but it should be noted that some s-systems do give good double solutions. In reality, this double solution will not be used, because the single-star fit is too good.

6. ASTROMETRIC ERRORS

As to the actual astrometric errors, there are several points to be made. For the s-systems, a single-star solution may be compared with either the primary component or with the photocentre. The latter is the obvious choice for a close double, but the former is more adequate for a well-separated system with a large magnitude difference. Barring the somewhat difficult intermediate region (0.2-0.4 arcsec), the single star rms-errors (eq. 1) are in the range 1-3 mas (depending on magnitude). The only significant discrepancies are for a few short-period astrometric pairs.

For the b-systems, the astrometric parameters for the photocentre are almost always well determined, while the relative coordinates for the two components are increasingly difficult to disentangle as the separation shrinks and/or the magnitude difference increases. Eq. (2) for the b/s-border suggests that one introduces the "effective magnitude difference"

$$\begin{aligned} dH_{\text{eff}} &= dH - 5.5 \lg(\text{sep}/0".32) & \text{sep} < ".32 \\ dH_{\text{eff}} &= dH & \text{sep} > ".32 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

There is then a clear relation between dH_{eff} and the relative rms-error (see Fig. 6), which may be approximated by quadratic relations

$$\text{rms}_{\text{rel}} = C_1 + C_2 * (dH_{\text{eff}})^2 \quad (4)$$

Typical values for C_1 and C_2 are given in Table 1. The astrometric errors for the photocentre may also be of some interest. They increase somewhat for large separations, thus the values given in Table 1 are for $\text{sep} < 0.4$ arcsec.

Fig. 6. Relative astrometric error (companion-primary) as function of dH_{eff} . ($H_1=8.5$, latitude 32°).

Table 1. Typical effective errors for the four "classes" of binaries in Figs. 2-5.

H_1	lat	obstime(sec)	C_1 (mas)	C_2 (mas)	rms (mas) pc
8.5	32°	502	1.2	0.8	0.7
6.0	32°	251	0.9	0.6	0.5
11.0	32°	502	3.4	1.6	1.8
8.5	12°	389	1.8:	0.8:	0.8

All the above concerns the astrometric parameters. It is also interesting to look briefly at the magnitudes. For several reasons (IDT profile, binning etc.), the observed intensities tend to be somewhat low, and there will also be complicated colour-effects. These "absolute" deviations are not in themselves important, what matters is the double star magnitudes as compared with the (standardized) values for singles. Using only the mean magnitude deviations (sol-true) for primary components ($\text{sep} > 0''.4$) and photocentres ($\text{sep} < 0''.2$), we find no systematic effects above the 1%-level.

The magnitude-differences given in the double solutions have small errors for $dH_{\text{eff}} < 2$. (Typical standard deviation 0.01 for $H_1=6$ to 0.07 for $H_1=11$). For larger dH_{eff} , the standard deviation is more often around 0.10 mag.

7. TRIPLE STAR DETECTION

The methods described above may be adapted also to finding an unknown third component to a known wide double (ref. 8). The double solution is obtained as before by iterating for the primary solution. A poor fit may indicate a resolvable third component, and a new grid iteration is performed as described in Section 5. (In many cases, the third component will be found close to the primary, but a search will have to be done around the secondary too.)

From the tests performed so far, this finding of a third component is not much different from finding an unknown double. The detection-limits in the $\text{sep}/\Delta m$ -plane will depend on the parameters of the wide double, but apparently rather weakly. (For a 15 arcsec double with equal components, we find $dH_{\text{max}} = 2.5$, $\text{sep}_{\text{min}} = 0''.15$.)

It is difficult to estimate the proportion of thus discoverable triples among the wide binaries, but the method proposed will certainly be applicable in several cases.

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REFERENCES

1. L Lindegren: Treatment of double stars in the overall NDAC data processing. (These proceedings.)
2. S Söderhjelm: HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, I. NDAC/LO/066 (NDAC working paper, Lund Observatory, Dec 1985)
3. S Söderhjelm: HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, Ib. NDAC/LO/067 (NDAC working paper, Lund Observatory, Feb 1986)
4. S Söderhjelm: HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, II. NDAC/LO/071 (NDAC working paper, Lund Observatory, Apr 1986)
5. S Söderhjelm: HIPPARCOS binaries: Error increase at 1 grid-period. NDAC/LO/073 (NDAC working paper, Lund Observatory, Jun 1986)
6. S Söderhjelm: HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, III. NDAC/LO/074 (NDAC working paper, Lund Observatory, Jun 1986)
7. S Söderhjelm: HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, IVa. NDAC/LO/080 (NDAC working paper, Lund Observatory, Sep 1986)
8. S Söderhjelm: HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, IVb. NDAC/LO/089 (NDAC working paper, Lund Observatory, Dec 1986)
9. L Lindegren and S Söderhjelm: Simulation software developed at the Lund Observatory. RGO simulation workshop, 21-22 sept 1986
10. S Söderhjelm: Statistical models for HIPPARCOS binaries. Astrophys. Sp. Sci. 110, 77, 1985
11. L Lindegren: Imaging properties of HIPPARCOS and the observation of multiple stars. Strasbourg Coll., ESA SP-177, p.147, 1982